

Optimization Techniques for Reducing False Positives in Decision Tree-Based Intrusion Detection Systems

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Optimization Techniques for Reducing False Positives in Decision Tree-Based Intrusion Detection Systems

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Abstract

This study investigates optimization techniques aimed at reducing false positives (FPs) in Decision Tree-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) in cybersecurity applications while focusing on maintaining a high level of accuracy while minimizing false positive rates (FPR), that may inundate security analysts and diminish the overall effectiveness of cybersecurity systems. A systematic review of 15 high-quality studies was carried out with a spotlight on three key optimization approaches: Hybrid and Ensemble Models, Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques, and Innovative Splitting Criteria. While the current literature explores various machine learning approaches, it lacks comprehensive insights into the best improvement techniques for minimizing FPs, which is one of the research objectives of this work. A classification and evaluation framework was developed to classify these techniques based on their effectiveness, applicability, and scalability, allowing cybersecurity researchers and practitioners to select the most suitable methods for their specific contexts. Additionally, a knowledge database was created, containing the research questions, methodologies, datasets, and outcomes from the reviewed studies, providing a valuable resource for future research. The findings indicated that Hybrid and Ensemble Models, particularly those combining decision trees with random forest and Naive Bayes, offer the best balance between detection accuracy and low FPR balance. For instance, hybrid models such as Random Tree + PART showed an accuracy rate of 91% and a FPR of 0.4%. Nevertheless, scalability and computational cost remain significant challenges. This research concludes that, although ensemble approaches are quite effective in reducing FPs, more progress is required to handle scalability issues in large-scale, real-time environments. Future research could focus on improving these techniques and exploring their real-world deployment.

Keywords

Decision Tree, Intrusion Detection Systems, False Positives, Optimization Techniques, Hybrid Models, Feature Selection, Splitting Criteria, Cybersecurity.

1. Introduction

The fast evolution of cyber threats has led to the creation of effective detection systems to safeguard important data and vital infrastructure assets from harm. Among these, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are essential for identifying and stopping malicious activity in networks [1]. Within IDS, Decision Tree models have stood out among the machine learning (ML) techniques used, because of their effectiveness in categorizing data and their capability to handle large datasets and provide easily interpretable decision rules easily grasped by security experts [2]. However, a significant issue with these models is their tendency to generate a high number of false positives (FPs) which can overwhelm security analysts by flagging benign activities as potential threats [3]. This not only increases the workload and demands on security teams but also diverts attention from genuine security breaches that require immediate action. Over time, due to false positives occur so frequently, security staff may eventually become "alert fatigue" and begin to minimize or ignore alarms, potentially allowing actual threats to go unnoticed. Moreover, this high false positive rate diminishes the system's overall efficiency, as computational resources are wasted processing non-malicious data, reducing the speed and accuracy of threat detection in the network.

In recent years, various optimization techniques have been suggested to reduce FPs in ML models, especially in Decision Trees used in IDS, including Hybrid and Ensemble Models along with Feature Selection techniques and Innovative Splitting Criteria. One of the proposed techniques, hybrid models, especially those that combine decision trees with techniques such as random forest and naive Bayes, have shown promising results in reducing FPs and maintaining high accuracy [4, 5, 6, 7]. Despite these advances, the problem remains, especially when moving from test scenarios to real-world environments where scalability, adaptability, and computational cost are major concerns [8].

The primary gap identified in the current literature is the lack of comprehensive assessment of the most effective optimization techniques for decreasing FPs in IDS that utilize Decision Tree models. While many optimization techniques have been proposed, a systematic classification and evaluation of these techniques is required in order to help practitioners and researchers choose the best techniques for specific scenarios. Additionally, there is a limited focus on how these methods function in real-world, large-scale settings. This research gap underscores the necessity to explore practical and scalable solutions for minimizing FPs.

This study aims to investigate and systematically review the optimization techniques employed to lower FPs in IDS based on Decision Trees. By focusing on strategies such as hybrid models and ensemble techniques alongside feature selection and Innovative Splitting Criteria methods, the goal is to provide a clearer understanding of the efficiency and scalability of these approaches in practice. The central research question guiding this study is: "What are the most effective optimization techniques for reducing false positives in Decision Tree models within Intrusion Detection Systems?". This question sets the stage for systematic review and analysis to ensure the research tackles the challenges and gaps in the current literature.

The research is based on a systematic literature review (SLR) of 15 high-quality research papers that address optimization techniques for minimizing FPs in IDS models. These chosen studies have been analyzed using thematic coding in ATLAS.ti software and classifying the approaches according to their efficiency and application context.

Through this research, hybrid and ensemble methods, particularly those involving Random Tree and Naive Bayes, were identified as the most promising approaches for achieving a balance between detection accuracy and low FPR. Moreover, a categorization and evaluation framework was created that can assist in choosing the appropriate optimization strategies for practical implementations, alongside a knowledge database that can help researchers and practitioners select the most suitable methods for their specific cybersecurity needs. In addition, recommendations were formulated based on the findings, tackling the practical challenges of implementing these methods in real-world settings.

This paper is organized as follows: The next section discusses the related work, providing a literature review of the optimization techniques currently in use. The methodology section explains how the systematic review was conducted and details the thematic coding techniques applied. In the results section, findings on various techniques' effectiveness are provided, followed by a discussion of the findings and implications for real-world deployment. Finally, in the conclusion section, key findings are recapped and recommendations for future research are made.

2. Literature Review

This section presents a systematic review of the literature concerning optimization techniques for decreasing FPs in Decision Tree-based IDS as a cybersecurity tool for detecting malicious activities effectively. In the context of IDS, false positives — incorrect alerts for benign activities — are a major issue, as they can overwhelm security teams and lead to alert fatigue, making it harder to identify real threats. Decision Tree models are widely used due to their simplicity and interpretability; however, they are prone to generate a higher number of FPs compared to more complex models, especially in dynamic and large-scale environments.

To address this, various optimization techniques have been proposed over the years to balance the trade-off between accuracy and false positive rates (FPR), without sacrificing the scalability and real-time applicability of these systems. This review follows a thematic approach and group studies based on three main themes: innovative

splitting criteria, hybrid and ensemble models, and feature selection and preprocessing techniques. Each of these themes has contributed to improving the performance of IDS by making the detection of cyber threats more precise, while simultaneously reducing the burden of false alarms. The scope of this review includes models that focus on decision tree models in IDS and that have been tested in both theoretical and practical cybersecurity scenarios to assess their suitability for real-world use in terms of applicability, scalability, and computational efficiency.

2.1 Innovative Splitting Criteria and Evaluation Methods

Numerous studies have explored new methods of dividing data in Decision Tree models to improve their performance in IDS. For example, Boutsinas and Tsekouronas [9] introduced a splitting criterion aimed at lowering FPs without compromising the overall accuracy of the model. This technique has outperformed traditional gain-based criteria significantly due to its effectiveness in smaller to mid-sized networks prioritizing FP reduction; however, its adaptability to bigger datasets is somewhat restricted. In a vein, Ohta et al. [10] put forward an alternative attribute evaluation function that notably decreased FPR, although it encountered performance issues as the system expanded in size.

2.2 Hybrid and Ensemble Models

Studies have also focused on integrating Decision Trees with other machine-learning techniques to decrease FPs. Hybrid and ensemble models have gained attention for their capability to leverage the advantages of multiple algorithms simultaneously. Studies by Goeschel [6] and Landress [11] demonstrated that hybrid models that integrate decision trees with other techniques such as support vector machines (SVM) Naive Bayes and clustering techniques like K-means enhance detection precision while minimizing FPR. The hybrid model of using Decision Trees and SVM in the study by Kumari and Mehta [12] successfully lowered the FPR to approximately 0.09% - 1.0%, with a high detection rate exceeding 99%. Although these methods have proven effective, in practice they encounter difficulties regarding scalability and computational expenses when deployed in real-time IDS setups. Furthermore, Farid et al. [5] explored the use of Naïve Bayesian Trees (NBTree), a model that incorporates Naïve Bayes classifiers into the Decision Tree structures leaves to enhance accuracy and decrease FPs, highlighting the benefits of hybrid approaches in cybersecurity.

2.3 Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques

Optimal feature selection and preprocessing play a role in fine-tuning Decision Tree models for maximum effectiveness, as they help the system concentrate on the most important data points. According to Pitre et al. [13], emphasize that there is a need to fine-tune feature selection to strike a balance between precision and reducing FPs. Feature selection methods such as particle swarm optimization (PSO) have been successfully combined with hybrid models, as seen in Kumari & Mehta's study [12], resulting in high detection accuracy but demanding significant computational effort for real-time applications. The studies show that preprocessing techniques are crucial for improving Decision Tree models in the field of cybersecurity.

2.4 Recent Developments

Recent studies have focused on hybrid models that combine advanced algorithms such as Logistic Regression and Decision Trees to improve the performance of IDS. The dual-phase model introduced by Pitre et al. [13] notably decreased FPR, underscoring the significance of ongoing enhancement in hybrid models. Similarly, Farid et al. [5] applied their study using a Self-Adaptive Naive Bayesian Tree method that performed well across most cyber-attack types; however, the FPs were notably high in certain attack categories such as R2L (Remote-to-Local).

In summary, the literature reveals that hybrid approaches, specifically those that merge Decision Trees with Naive Bayes, SVM, or clustering methods, strike a balance between accuracy and lowering FPR. However, hurdles

persist in terms of scalability and computational cost, particularly when transitioning from controlled environments to large-scale, real-time deployments [14]. Although advancements have been achieved so far, there is still a need for further research into crafting remedies for these constraints. This review highlights the gaps in the lack of a comprehensive evaluation of the most effective optimization techniques for mitigating vulnerabilities in vulnerability detection systems that use decision tree models, as well as the gap in scalability and practical use in real-world scenarios. This study seeks to address these gaps by presenting a more comprehensive framework for improving decision tree-based vulnerability detection systems. In addition, recommendations are formulated based on the findings to address the practical challenges of implementing these methods in real-world environments.

3. Methodology

This research adopts a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach to identify, evaluate, and categorize the most effective optimization techniques aimed at reducing FPs in Decision Tree-based IDS. Unique to the SLR method is its capability to offer a comprehensive and impartial analysis of existing research endeavors. Through an approach of gathering and reviewing high-quality research papers, the SLR provides insights into tested methodologies, tools, and techniques that have exhibited effectiveness in enhancing Decision Tree models within the realm of cybersecurity. By identifying gaps in existing studies, the SLR guarantees that this research brings forth insights and delves into areas that warrant further exploration. The primary research question steering this SLR is:

- What are the most effective optimization techniques for reducing false positives in Decision Tree models within Intrusion Detection Systems?

3.1 Research Design and Development

This project's research design revolves around a structured SLR protocol that adheres to the established guidelines of systematic reviews. This methodology is suitable as it enables the aggregation of results from multiple studies to analyze patterns, highlight gaps, and determine the best methods for minimizing FPs in IDS.

The SLR process was conducted through several separate stages:

3.1.1 Search Strategy:

A systematic search was conducted across reputable academic databases, such as IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink, ACM Digital Library, and Google Scholar. Keywords such as "Decision Tree optimization", "false positives", "cybersecurity", and "intrusion detection systems" were used to identify relevant research. Emphasis was placed on selecting articles published within the last two decades to ensure the review incorporated recent advancements in optimization techniques for Decision Tree models.

3.1.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Research papers were chosen based on specific inclusion criteria, including peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and high-quality research studies that focused on Decision Tree models and FPs in IDS within the field of cybersecurity. Studies that did not address Decision Tree models or that were unrelated to IDS, were excluded. Articles were also filtered based on relevance to the research questions and their practical applicability. A total of 183 documents were retrieved. All duplicate items have been removed. To identify potential articles, 63 documents were screened for their title and 39 documents for their abstract. To assess the relevance of the inclusion criteria, the full text of 25 documents was assessed. Ultimately, 15 studies were selected for data extraction and analysis. As shown in Figure 1, the process of including and selecting articles is depicted with the PRISMA Flow Diagram.

Fig 1. PRISMA flow diagram showing the process of study selection, including identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion in the systematic review.

3.1.3 Data Extraction, Management, and Quality Assessment:

A standardized data extraction form was created to systematically document key information from the studies chosen, such as the author(s), publication year, research questions, methodologies, machine learning models used, datasets used, optimization methods used, performance metrics (FPR and accuracy), main discoveries identified, strengths, weaknesses, and gaps observed. This approach facilitated a uniform analysis of all studies. The form is shown in Table 1. The data was structured using the reference management software EndNote for efficient storage and retrieval.

Table 1. Data Extraction Form Template for Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

Study Identification:	
Author(s)	
Year of Publication	
Title	
Study characteristics:	
Study aims/objectives:	
Primary Research Question	
Secondary Research Questions (if applicable):	
Study Methodology:	
Methodology Type	
Data Collection Method	
Study Design	
Machine Learning Models Used	
Datasets Used	
Optimization Techniques	

Performance Metrics:	
False Positive Rate (FPR)	
Accuracy	
Other Relevant Metrics	
Key Findings	
Strengths of the Study	
Weaknesses of the Study	
Considerations	
Gaps Observed	

In addition to the extraction process, Quality Assessment Tools were applied to gauge how strong the evidence was presented in each reviewed study. These tools helped to figure out how relevant and reliable the optimization methods discussed in the literature were. The assessment criteria considered factors like scalability and computational efficiency as how applicable the techniques were to real-world scenarios. These evaluation criteria are shown in Table 2 and ensure that only high-quality studies were included for synthesis.

Table 2. The evaluation criteria and checklists were applied to gauge how strong the evidence

Section	Criterion	Description	Score (1-5)
Study Relevance and Scope	Relevance to Research Question	Does the study address Decision Tree optimization for IDS and focus on reducing false positives?	
	Applicability to Real-World Scenarios	Are the techniques tested in real-world environments and applicable across different network settings?	
Methodological Rigor	Research Design	Is the research design appropriate and is the methodology clearly described for replication?	
	Dataset Quality	Is the dataset relevant (e.g., KDD, NSL-KDD)? Are limitations or biases discussed?	
Performance Metrics	Performance Reporting	Are accuracy and FPR metrics reported? Are the results statistically validated?	
	Comparison with Baseline Methods	Is the technique compared with existing models, including hybrid or ensemble methods?	
Scalability and Efficiency	Scalability Assessment	Can the optimization technique scale to large or complex IDS networks? Are scalability challenges discussed?	
	Computational Efficiency	Are computational costs or resource requirements assessed? Is the method feasible for real-time applications?	
Strengths, Weaknesses, and Limitations	Critical Analysis	Does the study discuss its strengths, weaknesses, and limitations?	
	Suggestions for Future Research	Are recommendations for further research or improvements provided? Are research gaps identified?	

3.2 Data Collection Methods:

The process of gathering data included conducting an exhaustive search for relevant studies in the chosen databases, with a main emphasis on optimization methods applied to Decision Tree models in IDS. The studies were evaluated based on their significance in cybersecurity and how they helped decrease FP in IDS.

After identifying the studies in question and thoroughly reviewing them. The following data was extracted for analysis:

- The technique of optimization utilized (e.g., hybrid models, ensemble methods, feature selection techniques, innovative splitting criteria).
- The dataset utilized in the research studies (e.g., KDD and NSL-KDD).
- The metrics related to performance, specifically the rates of FP as well, as the accuracy rates overall.
- The most important findings were identified from each study.
- The strengths, weaknesses, and gaps that were observed.
- Scalability and computational cost considerations.

This method guaranteed a comprehensive dataset of studies that directly address the research questions.

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques:

The qualitative synthesis of the studies was conducted using thematic analysis. Where recurring themes and patterns can be identified related to optimization techniques used for reducing FPs in IDS. The analysis centered on three main themes:

1. **Hybrid and ensemble models:** These models merge Decision Trees with other models such as Random Forests and Naive Bayes to boost accuracy and minimize FPs.
2. **Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques:** Refining input data using techniques to select the relevant features, for Decision Tree models is essential, for enhancing performance.
3. **Innovative Splitting Criteria:** Creative Ways to Improve Decision Making, in Decision Trees Aimed at Reducing Errors and FPs.

The analysis was carried out using ATLAS.ti software, which provided a structured coding environment for organizing and analyzing qualitative data. Each study was classified according to its approach and evaluated for its success in decreasing FPs.

3.4 Validation and Limitations of the Methodology:

To confirm the accuracy and trustworthiness of the results obtained in the study, several validation steps were taken:

- Triangulation of the findings was performed by comparing the results from multiple studies to ensure consistency and accuracy.
- Quality Assessment Tools were employed to measure the strength and relevance of each study. The tools evaluated key aspects such as scalability, computational efficiency, and real-world applicability (shown in Table 2).
- The inclusion of diverse data sources from trusted databases helped provide an overview of the research in this field and made the findings more widely applicable.

The methodology used was cross-referenced with similar SLR studies in related areas to confirm that the techniques applied were in line with standard research practices.

Nevertheless, some constraints need to be recognized. To begin with, although the SLR provides an encompassed perspective of the research landscape, its scope is restricted by the availability of relevant studies, and some emerging techniques may not yet be represented in the literature. Moreover, the review heavily depends on

publicly available datasets means that certain proprietary optimization techniques used in the industry might not be included. In addition, further exploration is needed to assess how well the techniques reviewed can be used in real-world situations and expanded to a scale because most of the conclusions are drawn from controlled experiments or simulations.

To summarize, The SLR conducted in this study allowed for a comprehensive and structured exploration of optimization techniques for reducing FPs in IDS models based on Decision Trees. The methods employed ensured thorough data gathering, analysis, and validation, yielding insights into effective optimization strategies and pinpointing gaps research may involve implementing these methods in real-world settings. Future work could focus on testing these techniques in real-time environments to address these gaps.

By following this rigorous approach in the study's methodology, this research provides valuable insights about enhancing Decision Tree models in the field of cybersecurity and sets the stage for future exploration, on enhancing their effectiveness in minimizing FPs.

4. Results

The main goal of this study was to identify and evaluate the most effective optimization techniques for decreasing FPs in Decision Tree models applied in IDS. Systematic search across databases including IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink, ACM Digital Library, and Google Scholar yielded a collection of research papers on enhancing the performance of decision tree models in IDS. The keyword search, focusing on terms like "Decision Tree optimization," "false positives," and "cybersecurity," resulted in 183 initial articles. Following the application of inclusion/exclusion criteria, a total of 15 studies were chosen for in-depth analysis. Through SLR, the extracted data from the selected studies were categorized into three core themes of optimization techniques: Hybrid and Ensemble Models, Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques, and Innovative Splitting Criteria. The effectiveness of these methods was evaluated by their ability to enhance accuracy while keeping FPR to a minimum. This results section outlines the findings derived from the synthesis of the selected research.

From the 15 analyzed studies, the following results emerged:

4.1 Optimization Techniques

- **Feature Selection:** Various research papers have pointed out that using feature selection techniques enhances the accuracy of decision trees and decreases the occurrence of FPs in a way with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Genetic Algorithms being recognized as particularly successful methods but increased computational costs [12, 13, 15, 16].
- **Hybrid and Ensemble Models:** A prominent result was that combining decision trees with Naive Bayes, Random Forest, SVM, and other algorithms in hybrid and ensemble models notably decreased FPs and they are the most effective in reducing false positives (FPR) [4, 5, 6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18]. A study demonstrated that using a Random Tree + PART hybrid model led to a decrease in FPR to 0.4%, Achieving an accuracy rate of, up to 91% [7].
- **Innovative Splitting Criteria:** Another critical result was the utilizing advanced splitting criteria like modifying the Gini index or employing custom threshold algorithms which led to enhanced decision tree effectiveness, in IDS. Especially in smaller to mid-sized networks, but the scalability of larger datasets remains a challenge. [9, 10, 17, 19].

4.2 Optimization Technique Distribution

The systematic literature review revealed that Hybrid and Ensemble Models dominate significantly, as shown in the pie chart below Figure 2. Half of the studies (56%) centered on this particular category underscored the

extensive adoption of model combination techniques. Both Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques along with Innovative Splitting Criteria each had a representation of 22%.

Fig 2. Optimization Technique Distribution

This distribution emphasizes that hybrid techniques play a significant role in minimizing FPs, reflecting the growing trend in cybersecurity to combine various models for enhanced detection accuracy.

4.3 Performance Metrics and False Positive Rates

A comparison of the accuracy and FPR across different optimization methods, it becomes apparent that the hybrid models excel in terms of performance metrics. The bar chart below Figure 3 summarizes the performance of these techniques and outlines their consistently high accuracy exceeding 90% alongside consistently low FPR that generally stays below 1%.

Fig 3. Comparison of Accuracy and FPR Across Optimization Techniques

For instance, the hybrid approach combining SVM, Decision Trees, and Naive Bayes attained a 99.62% accuracy and 1.57% FPR. On the other hand, the ID3 Decision Tree Retraining strategy achieved an accuracy of 100% utilizing iterative retraining methods. Notably, models that combine various approaches tend to outperform standalone methods, particularly in environments requiring real-time analysis.

4.4 Detailed Categorization and Evaluation Framework of Optimization Techniques

The following framework Table 3 summarizes the key optimization techniques, their performance metrics, applicability, and limitations, offering a comprehensive comparison of the techniques identified in the reviewed studies.

Table 3. a categorization and evaluation framework for Comparison of Optimization Techniques that decrease FPs in IDS

Optimization Technique	Performance Metrics	Source (APA 7)	Technique Category	Optimization Focus	Applicability	Suitability for Use Cases	Complexity and Scalability	Challenges/Limitations
Hybrid Data Mining and Decision Tree	- FPR: 0.08% (Normal), 0.0018% (DoS) - Accuracy: 99.92% (Normal)	Anuar et al. (2008)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models and Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques	Reduce misclassification of attacks and false positives	Network traffic analysis, IDS (KDD Cup 99 dataset)	Suitable for classifying DOS, R2L, and normal traffic.	Moderate complexity, scalable to large datasets	Struggles with rare attack types (e.g., U2R), requires frequent updates to data and attributes for accuracy improvement
Association Rule Mining with Decision Trees (J48)	Accuracy: 99.2%, FPR: 0.009	Awad (2021)	Innovative Splitting Criteria and Evaluation Methods	Model Evaluation and Enhancement	Network Intrusion Detection	Large-Scale IDS Networks	Medium	Challenges in adapting to new and emerging network behaviours.
False-Positives Splitting Criterion	Increased classification accuracy, reduced false positives compared to Gain criterion	Boutsinas & Tsekouronas (2004)	Innovative Splitting Criteria and Evaluation Methods	False-Positive Reduction Focus	General Cybersecurity	Suitable for small to medium networks, where false positives are critical.	Medium, requires tuning of parameters like Count-zero	Limited performance improvements for larger datasets or more complex scenarios
K-Means Clustering with K-NN and Decision Table	- Accuracy: 96.55% - Detection Rate: 93.67% - FPR: 0.019%	Chordia & Gupta (2015)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models and Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques	Combining clustering (K-Means), K-NN classification, and Decision Table for false positive reduction	Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS)	Best for environments with high volume of attacks (DoS, U2R, R2L, Probe)	Moderate to High complexity due to combination of multiple techniques	Requires fine-tuning of clustering and classification; potential computational overhead for large-scale systems
Hybrid Model (Naive Bayes + Decision Tree)	- DR: 99.76% (Normal), 99.21% (Probe), 99.65% (DoS), 99.11% (U2R), 99.16% (R2L) n- FPR: 0.07% (Normal), 0.05% (DoS), 0.44% (Probe), 6.85% (R2L)	Farid et al. (2010)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models	Model Combination	Intrusion Detection	Large Networks	Medium Complexity	High FPR for R2L class
Hybrid Model (Naive Bayes + Decision Tree)	DR: 99.72% (Normal), 99.25% (Probe), 99.75% (DoS), 99.20% (U2R), 99.26% (R2L); FP: 0.06% (Normal), 0.39% (Probe), 0.04% (DoS), 0.11% (U2R), 6.81% (R2L)	Farid et al. (2010)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models	Combining Naive Bayes and Decision Tree for adaptive IDS	Network-based IDS	Large-scale networks	Medium	High FP in R2L attacks; computationally intensive for real-time IDS
Hybrid Model (SVM, Decision Trees, Naive Bayes)	Accuracy: 99.62%, FPR: 1.57%, DR: 99.81%	Goeschel (2016)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models	Model Combination	General Cybersecurity	Large Networks	Medium	High computational cost, not scalable for real-time IDS
Hybrid Model (Random Tree + PART)	Accuracy: 91.5%, FPR: 0.4%	Kshirsagar & Joshi (2016)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models	Model Combination	General Cybersecurity, IDS	Suitable for large datasets and live traffic analysis	Medium Complexity	Computational cost and resource requirements in real-time systems.

Hybrid Model: J48 Decision Tree + SVM with PSO Feature Selection	- Accuracy: 99.1%-99.2% - Detection Rate: 99.6% - FPR: 0.9%-1.0%	Kumari & Mehta (2020)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models and Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques	Reduce false positives by integrating DT and SVM using an ensemble approach and PSO for feature selection	Intrusion detection systems (IDS)	Suitable for high-performance IDS environments with a focus on low false alarm rates and high detection accuracy	Moderate complexity; PSO requires additional computational effort for feature selection, and integrating multiple models increases complexity	Computational overhead due to ensemble technique; needs careful tuning of parameters for optimal performance
K-means, J48 Decision Tree, SOM Hybrid	Accuracy: 99.96% FPR: 0.30397%	Landress (2016)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models	Feature Selection, Clustering	Network Intrusion Detection	Large and complex networks, high traffic environments	Medium, significant computational demands	High computational cost, may not scale well for real-time IDS
Custom Attribute Evaluation for Decision Tree	FPR reduced to 22.2%-42.1% of original. Accuracy improved after leaf rewriting	Ohta, Kurebayashi, & Kobayashi (2008)	Innovative Splitting Criteria and Evaluation Methods	Minimize False Positives	Cybersecurity Intrusion Detection Systems	Medium-Large Networks	High computational cost, performance degradation with scaling	Limited applicability due to reliance on specialized datasets
Hybrid Model (Logistic Regression, Feature Selection, Two-Stage Model)	Stage 1: Accuracy: 0.932; Stage 2: Accuracy: 0.951 FPR significantly reduced after fine-tuning	Pitre et al. (2022)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models and Feature Selection and Preprocessing Techniques	Reduce False Positives and Improve Accuracy	General Cybersecurity	IDS for Zero-Day Attacks	Medium	High computational cost, fine-tuning required to balance false positives and negatives
ID3 Decision Tree Retraining	Accuracy: 100% after iterative retraining FPR: reduced through iterative learning	Vasseur (2018)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models and Innovative Splitting Criteria and Evaluation Methods	Iterative learning and retraining	General cybersecurity scenarios	Network-based IDS, continuous real-time monitoring	Medium complexity, scalable to large networks	Requires continuous retraining and may involve high computation costs
C4.5 and SVM Hybrid Approach	- FPR: SVM better (lower FPR) - Detection: C4.5 better (Probe, U2R, DOS)	We & Ye (2008), as cited in Gupta et al. (2016)	Hybrid and Ensemble Models	Reduce false positives by combining C4.5's accuracy and SVM's lower FPR	Intrusion detection systems, anomaly detection	Best for mixed attack environments (Probe, DOS, U2R)	Moderate complexity; SVM can be resource-intensive	Limited to offline analysis; outdated dataset (KDD99); balancing detection accuracy with low FPR remains challenging

4.5 Datasets used

Studies utilizing the KDD and NSL-KDD datasets consistently demonstrated improvements in intrusion detection while minimizing false alarms, particularly when hybrid models were utilized. However, a recurring limitation of the studies is the reliance on datasets such as KDD99, a widely used but outdated dataset for evaluating IDS [18, 20]. It may not fully represent modern network environments. This raises concerns about the generalizability of the results.

4.6 Performance Metrics

Across all studies, there was a consistent improvement in FPR. The Random Tree + PART hybrid model showed the highest reduction in FPR, whereas decision trees without ensemble methods resulted in higher FPR values. Many models faced challenges balancing high detection rates and low false positives, especially when detecting complex attacks or rare threats like R2L and U2R.

4.7 Scalability and Computational Cost

Despite the progress made in FPR and accuracy levels, most studies have highlighted difficulties related to computational costs and scalability issues. Many models have been tested in controlled environments and on small-scale networks, raising doubts about their ability to scale to larger, dynamic networks in real-time scenarios, especially when advanced optimization techniques such as feature selection are used in combination with hybrid approaches. Furthermore, hybrid models and custom evaluation functions often increase computational complexity, making their implementation in real-time detection systems more difficult. Several studies have also warned of the risk of overfitting, especially when models are heavily optimized for specific datasets such as KDD99, which may not fully represent modern network environments [21].

4.8 Secondary Results

- Several research papers have delved into the balance between detecting accuracy and scalability trade-offs. Hybrid approaches notably brought down FPs considerably, however, they required higher computational resources and posed challenges in terms of scalability when dealing with larger datasets.
- Limited exploration of emerging threats, as many models focused on traditional attacks (e.g., DDoS, probe, R2L, U2R), but did not adequately address new emerging threats such as advanced persistent threats (APTs) or complex multi-vector attacks [22].

4.9 Anomalous Results

A few studies reported conflicting findings when it came to feature selection, not resulting in a significant decrease in FPs. This was attributed to constraints in the datasets used or the application of suboptimal optimization techniques.

4.10 knowledge database

Alongside the table summarizing the optimization techniques, a knowledge database shown in Table 4 in the [Appendix](#), was created to capture the detailed characteristics of each reviewed study. This database includes the research questions, methodologies, datasets used, optimization techniques employed, and the performance metrics of each paper, which provides additional context and a comprehensive comparison of the findings. The knowledge database is presented as supplementary material and provides a valuable resource for future researchers to explore the impact of different optimization strategies on false positive reduction.

5. Discussion

5.1 Summary of Main Findings

This research highlighted three primary optimization techniques that proved effective in minimizing FPs in decision tree-based IDS models:

- Hybrid and Ensemble Models were consistently dominant as the most effective strategies for reducing FPs in IDS. According to the Distribution of Optimization Techniques analysis, findings showed that more than half of the studies reviewed utilized hybrid approaches. These techniques are particularly effective at handling complex datasets and ever-changing network traffic while upholding high accuracy and minimal FPR as low, as 0.4%. Nevertheless, employing these models entails challenges and considerations as computational and scalability costs.
- Feature Selection Techniques, although effective in some cases, provided mixed results based on the dataset and optimization approach used. Though techniques such as PCA and Genetic Algorithms exhibit improvements, in some cases; however, they may still necessitate fine-tuning.
- Innovative Splitting Criteria have been shown to enhance the decision-making process of decision trees, yielding better results in terms of accuracy and reduced FPR.

5.2 Interpretation of Results

The results indicate that hybrid models hold the most potential for practical application in real-world IDS environments where minimizing FPs is paramount. The focus on hybrid and ensemble models is due to their

ability to combine the strengths of multiple classifiers. However, the trade-off between improved detection and increased computational cost must be carefully considered, particularly for large-scale implementations.

The findings also confirm that Hybrid and Ensemble Models outperformed other techniques by reducing FPs while maintaining high accuracy, as shown in Fig 3 and they are essential for optimizing IDS, which confirms that it is the most effective optimization technique to reduce false positives in decision tree models within intrusion detection systems. Moreover, combining models and enhancing feature selection techniques significantly reduces false positives in complex environments.

5.3 Comparison with Prior Work

In comparison to previous studies, which largely focused on traditional models or isolated optimization techniques, this study adopts a more extensive approach by systematically reviewing and assessing numerous advanced techniques. Previous studies tended to highlight single techniques like Decision Tree models or uncomplicated feature selection strategies, often overlooking the potential presented by hybrid and ensemble approaches. Nonetheless, hybrid models - like those merging Random Tree with PART—have proven to be especially efficient providing both flexibility and scalability. These models demonstrate superior performance across various datasets, validating their potential for reducing false positives (FPs) in high-traffic environments, including network intrusion detection.

The key gap identified in the literature is the absence of a comprehensive evaluation framework that can systematically assess the most effective optimization techniques for reducing FPs in IDS based on Decision Tree models. Although individual studies have proposed various optimization approaches, there is limited focus on providing researchers and practitioners with clear guidance for selecting appropriate techniques based on specific scenarios. Moreover, current studies seldom delve into the effectiveness of these methods, in real-life scenarios at a scale prompting concerns about their scalability and practical usefulness.

This study addresses the gap by classifying and evaluating optimization techniques through a systematic literature review (SLR), focusing on hybrid models, feature selection, and innovative splitting criteria. It aligns solutions with real-world challenges in IDS deployments, bridging the gap between theory and practice and offering a roadmap for future research and practical applications in large-scale cybersecurity contexts.

5.4 Implications

The findings, from this study have implications that are significant for the field of cybersecurity particularly in the development of IDS models. By leveraging hybrid models and feature selection techniques, network administrators can implement IDS solutions that effectively lower FPs without sacrificing precision levels. This research can be used as a foundation for further exploration into optimizing decision trees while addressing the challenges of scalability and computational efficiency. In addition, the categorization and evaluation framework that was created can assist in choosing the appropriate optimization strategies for practical implementations, alongside a knowledge database that can help researchers and practitioners in selecting the most suitable methods for their specific cybersecurity needs.

5.5 Limitations

One limitation highlighted in this study is the issue of scalability. Although hybrid models demonstrate high performance, they also come with higher computational costs and intricacy, as shown in the framework Table 1. Techniques like K-Means Clustering with K-NN and Decision Tables demand significant computational resources, making them less scalable for real-time environments [16]. Additionally, certain models face difficulties in handling rare attack types, such as U2R and R2L, where minimizing positives proves to be trickier. Finally, the use of datasets such as KDD and NSL-KDD may limit the generalizability of the findings across different IDS.

5.6 Suggestions for Future Research

Future studies could explore the following areas:

- Developing more computationally efficient hybrid models while also keeping false positive rates low without the need for extensive computational resources.
- Adding more recent and varied datasets to the dataset pool in order to confirm that these methods are generally applicable.
- Exploring real-time optimization methods that can be applied to IDS without compromising performance with demanding computational requirements.
- Creating automated and real-time techniques that can better adapt to dynamic network environments and emerging threats, enhancing the overall efficiency of IDS.

6. Conclusion

This study's main focus was identifying and evaluating the most effective optimization techniques for decreasing false positives (FPs) in Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) based on Decision Trees. The research question aimed to explore which techniques – Hybrid and Ensemble Models, Feature Selection and Preprocessing, or Innovative Splitting Criteria – offer the best balance between detection accuracy and reduction of FPs in cybersecurity contexts. After conducting a systematic literature review of 15 high-quality studies, the results indicated that Hybrid and Ensemble Models combining Decision Trees with Random Forest and Naive Bayes stood out as superior to other approaches. These models consistently achieved accuracy levels reaching up to 99% while also keeping a low FPR of less than 1%.

The findings of this study have implications for enhancing IDS in the real world where reducing FPs is crucial. It's worth noting that although Hybrid Models showed promising results in terms of effectiveness and performance but their computational requirements and scalability present challenges in real-time large-scale environments. Additionally promising are feature selection methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Genetic Algorithms. in decreasing FPs, although their results varied depending on the dataset used.

One significant limitation of this study is the high computational cost linked to advanced optimization methods, which hinders their adaptability, in real-time setups. Furthermore, the utilization of KDD and NSL-KDD datasets limits the generalizability of the findings to other IDS contexts.

Future research should focus on addressing the computational costs and scalability issues associated with these models to facilitate their deployment in large-scale, real-time environments. By continuing to refine these techniques and explore new datasets, cybersecurity systems can become more adaptable and resilient in combating evolving threats.

In conclusion, this study offers valuable insights into optimizing IDS based on Decision Trees by identifying and evaluating techniques that effectively reduce FPs. By focusing on Hybrid and Ensemble Models, which demonstrated superior performance, this research lays groundwork for developing more accurate and scalable IDS solutions in cybersecurity. These results have implications that go beyond academic research and provide practical solutions for real-world cybersecurity challenges, where minimizing false alarms is crucial, for improving threat detection and response effectiveness. This work not only bridges a critical gap in the current literature but also serves as a roadmap for future advancements in IDS technologies, ensuring more secure and reliable networks in an increasingly connected world.

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References

- [1] I. Sharafaldin, A. Habibi Lashkari, and A. Ghorbani, "Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy (ICISSP)*, 2018, pp. 108-116. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5220/0006639801080116>
- [2] A. L. Buczak and E. Guven, "A Survey of Data Mining and Machine Learning Methods for Cyber Security Intrusion Detection," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 1153-1176, 2016. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2015.2494502>.
- [3] J. Ghadermazi, A. Shah, and S. Jajodia, "A Machine Learning and Optimization Framework for Efficient Alert Management in a Cybersecurity Operations Center," *Digital Threats*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 1–23, 2024. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3644393>.
- [4] M. D. Farid, N. Harbi, and M. Z. Rahman, "Combining Naive Bayes and Decision Tree for Adaptive Intrusion Detection," *arXiv*, 2010. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1005.4496>.
- [5] M. D. Farid, N. H. Hoa, J. Darmont, N. Harbi, and M. Z. Rahman, "Scaling up detection rates and reducing false positives in intrusion detection using NBTree," *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 64, pp. 165–169, 2010.
- [6] K. Goeschel, "Reducing false positives in intrusion detection systems using data-mining techniques utilizing support vector machines, decision trees, and naive Bayes for off-line analysis," in *Proc. IEEE SoutheastCon*, 2016, pp. 1–6. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/SECON.2016.7506774>.
- [7] V. Kshirsagar and M. Joshi, "Enhancing Intrusion Detection System by Reducing the False Positives through Application of Various Data Mining Techniques," *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 76, 2016.
- [8] K. Shaukat, S. Luo, V. Varadharajan, I. A. Hameed, S. Chen, D. Liu, and J. Li, "Performance comparison and current challenges of using machine learning techniques in cybersecurity," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 2509, 2020. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13102509>.
- [9] B. Boutsinas and I. X. Tsekouronas, "Splitting data in decision trees using the new false-positives criterion," in *Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence (Subseries of Lecture Notes in Computer Science)*, vol. 3025, pp. 174–182, 2004. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-24674-9_19.
- [10] S. Ohta, R. Kurebayashi, and K. Kobayashi, "Minimizing False Positives of a Decision Tree Classifier for Intrusion Detection on the Internet," *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 399–419, 2008. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10922-008-9102-4>.
- [11] A. D. Landress, "A hybrid approach to reducing the false positive rate in unsupervised machine learning intrusion detection," in *Proc. IEEE SoutheastCon*, 2016, pp. 1–6. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/SECON.2016.7506773>.
- [12] A. Kumari and A. K. Mehta, "A Hybrid Intrusion Detection System Based on Decision Tree and Support Vector Machine," in *Proc. 2020 IEEE 5th International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation (ICCCA)*, 2020, pp. 396–400. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCA49541.2020.9250753>.
- [13] P. Pitre, A. Gandhi, V. Konde, R. Adhao, and V. Pachghare, "An Intrusion Detection System for Zero-Day Attacks to Reduce False Positive Rates," in *Proc. 2022 International Conference for Advancement in Technology (ICONAT)*, 2022, pp. 1–6. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICONAT53423.2022.9726105>.
- [14] K. Shaukat, S. Luo, V. Varadharajan, I. A. Hameed, and M. Xu, "A Survey on Machine Learning Techniques for Cyber Security in the Last Decade," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 222310–222354, 2020. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3041951>.
- [15] N. B. Anuar, H. Sallehudin, A. Gani, and O. Zakari, "Identifying false alarm for network intrusion detection system using hybrid data mining and decision tree," *Malaysian Journal of Computer Science*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 101–115, 2008. Available: <https://doi.org/10.22452/mjcs.vol21no2.3>.
- [16] A. S. Chordia and S. Gupta, "An effective model for anomaly IDS to improve the efficiency," in *Proc. 2015 International Conference on Green Computing and Internet of Things (ICGCIOT)*, 2015, pp. 190–194. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICGCIOT.2015.7380455>.
- [17] P. R. Vasseur, "A machine learning approach to verify and reduce false positive alarms generated by data breach detection processes," Ph.D. dissertation, 2018. Available: <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/machine-learning-approach-verify-reduce-false/docview/2305833827/se-2>.
- [18] S.-Y. Wu and E. Yen, "Data mining-based intrusion detectors," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 5605–5612, 2009. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2008.06.138>.
- [19] N. A. Awad, "Enhancing network intrusion detection model using machine learning algorithms," *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 979–990, 2021. Available: <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2021.014307>.

[20] H. Hindy, D. Brosset, E. Bayne, A. Secam, C. Tachtatzis, R. Atkinson, and X. Bellekens, "A taxonomy and survey of intrusion detection system design techniques, network threats, and datasets," *ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 35, 2018. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/nnnnnnn.nnnnnnn>.

[21] J. Martinez Torres, C. Iglesias Comesana, and P. J. Garcia-Nieto, "Review: machine learning techniques applied to cybersecurity," *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 2823–2836, 2019. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13042-018-00906-1>.

[22] N. Gupta, K. Srivastava, and A. Sharma, "Reducing false positive in intrusion detection system: a survey," *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1600-1603, 2016.

Appendix

Knowledge database:

This knowledge database provides a comprehensive summary of 15 research papers, detailing their research questions, methodologies, machine learning models, datasets, optimization techniques, performance metrics, key findings, strengths, and weaknesses, focusing on improving intrusion detection systems (IDS) by reducing false positives.

Table 4. The knowledge database compiles key data from the 15 reviewed studies into a comprehensive resource

source	Research Questions	Methodologies	Machine Learning Models Used	Datasets Used	Optimization Methods Used	Performance Metrics	Main Discoveries Identified	Strengths	Weaknesses
Anuar, N. B., Sallehudin, H., Gani, A., & Zakari, O. (2009). Identifying false alarm for network intrusion detection system using hybrid data mining and decision tree. <i>Malaysian Journal of Computer Science</i> , 21(2), 101-115. https://doi.org/10.22452/mjcs.vol21no2.3	How can hybrid data mining and Decision Tree classification reduce false positives in IDS?	Hybrid data mining and Decision Tree (C5.0 algorithm)	Decision Tree (C5.0)	KDD Cup 99	Data mining with Decision Tree (C5.0 algorithm)	Accuracy: 99.92%, FPR: 0.08%	Hybrid model significantly reduces false positives while improving detection	Significant improvement in false positive reduction	Overfitting concerns
Awad, N. A. (2021). Enhancing network intrusion detection model using machine learning algorithms. <i>Computers, Materials & Continua</i> , 67(1), 979-990. https://doi.org/10.32604/comc.2021.014307	How can integration of machine learning algorithms enhance network IDS?	Naive Bayes, SVM, KNN	Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, SVM	KDD 99	Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, SVM	Accuracy: 99.2%, FPR: 0.009%	J48 most effective, SVM had lower false positives	J48 model highly accurate	SVM requires high computational resources
Boutsimas, B., & Tsokouras, I. X. (2004). Splitting data in decision trees using the new false-positives criterion. <i>Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence (Subseries of Lecture Notes in Computer Science)</i> , 3025, 174-182. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-24874-9_19	- How effective is the new False-Positives splitting criterion in reducing false positives compared to traditional criteria like Gain, Gain Ratio, Gini, and Twoing?	Proposed a new False-Positives criterion for splitting data in Decision Trees, focusing on minimizing false positives.	Decision Trees (ID3, C4.5)	Real-world dataset from Molecular Biology (promoter recognition problem)	False-Positives splitting criterion.	Increased classification accuracy, reduced false positives compared to Gain criterion	False-Positives criterion effectively reduces false positives and maintains comparable accuracy.	Focused on reducing false positives, tested across multiple datasets.	Complexity in implementation, bias toward attributes with many values, limited scope for other metrics.
Chordia, A. S., & Gupta, S. (2015). An effective model for anomaly IDS to improve the efficiency. 2015 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON GREEN COMPUTING AND INTERNET OF THINGS (ICGCIOT), 190-194. https://doi.org/10.1109/ICGCIOT.2015.7388455	How can different data mining techniques improve the efficiency and accuracy of anomaly-based IDS?	K-Means Clustering, Decision Table Majority Rule	K-Means, KNN, Decision Table	KDD99	K-Means Clustering, KNN	Accuracy: 96.55%, FPR: 0.019%	Decision Table Majority Rule reduced false positives	Highly effective reduction in false positives	Computational cost
Farid, M. D., Harbi, N., & Rahman, M. Z. (2019). Combining Naive Bayes and Decision Tree for Adaptive Intrusion Detection. <i>arXiv.Org</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1905.0496	How can combining Naive Bayes and Decision Tree improve IDS in terms of detection rates and false positives?	Naive Bayes, Decision Tree hybridization	Naive Bayes, Decision Tree	KDD99	Naive Bayes combined with Decision Tree	- DR: 99.76% (Normal), 99.21% (Probe), 99.65% (DoS), 99.11% (U2R), 99.16% (R2L) - FPR: 0.07% (Normal), 0.05% (DoS), 0.44% (Probe), 6.85% (R2L)	Naive Bayes combined with Decision Tree improves accuracy and reduces false positives	Hybrid algorithm effectively reduces false positives	Dataset limitations
Farid, M. D., Hoo, N. H., Darmont, J., Harbi, N., & Rahman, M. Z. (2019). Scaling up detection rates and reducing false positives in intrusion detection using NBTree. <i>World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology</i> , 64, 165-169.	How can an improved Naive Bayesian Tree algorithm be used to enhance detection rates and reduce false positives in network intrusion detection systems?	Hybrid approach using the NBTree algorithm, where decision tree nodes handle traditional splitting while Naive Bayesian classifiers are applied at the leaves.	NBTree (Naive Bayesian Tree) - a hybrid of Decision Trees and Naive Bayes classifiers.	KDD99	- Improved Self-Adaptive Naive Bayesian Tree (ISANBT) - Partitioning strategy based on attribute utility for optimal node splitting.	DR: 99.72% (Normal), 99.25% (Probe), 99.75% (DoS), 99.20% (U2R), 99.26% (R2L); FP: 0.06% (Normal), 0.39% (Probe), 0.04% (DoS), 0.11% (U2R), 6.81% (R2L)	The NBTree algorithm significantly improves detection rates and reduces false positives compared to traditional methods.	Balanced performance in both detection accuracy and false positive reduction.	Computational complexity and limited validation in real-world environments.

Goeschel, K. (2016). Reducing false positives in intrusion detection systems using data-mining techniques utilizing support vector machines, decision trees, and naive Bayes for off-line analysis. <i>Conference Proceedings - IEEE SOUTHEASTCON, 2016-</i> , 1-6. https://doi.org/10.1109/SECON.2016.7506774	How effectively can a hybrid model combining SVM, Decision Trees, and Naive Bayes reduce false positives in IDS?	The study uses a hybrid model combining SVM (Support Vector Machine) with Decision Trees (J48) and Naive Bayes for off-line analysis of intrusion detection data.	SVM, Decision Trees (J48), and Naive Bayes	KDDCup99	Hybrid model combining SVM for initial classification, Decision Trees for further classification, and Naive Bayes for voting on unclassified attacks.	Accuracy: 99.62%, FPR: 1.57%,	The hybrid model successfully reduced false positives while maintaining high accuracy.	High accuracy (99.95%) and significant reduction in false positives (FPR of 1.57%).	Computational cost of the decision tree component, especially with large datasets.
Quota, N., Srivastava, K., & Sharma, A. (2015). Reducing false positive in intrusion detection system: a survey. <i>International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies</i> , 7(3), 1600-1603.	How do machine learning models reduce false alarms in IDS?	Survey of decision trees and alert reduction	Survey of multiple algorithms	Various	Hybrid machine learning models	Various improvements in detection rate	Survey showed effective alert reduction methods	Strong survey of alert reduction methods	Limited dataset generalizability
Kahrsagar, V., & Joshi, M. (2016). Enhancing Intrusion Detection System by Reducing the False Positives through Application of Various Data Mining Techniques. <i>International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security</i> , 14(2), 76.	How can a hybrid approach using multiple data mining techniques improve accuracy and reduce false positives in IDS?	Hybrid Random Tree and PART	Random Tree + PART	KDD 99	Hybrid Random Tree + PART algorithm	Accuracy: 91.5%, FPR: 0.4%	Hybrid Random Tree and PART algorithm effectively reduces false positives	Effective hybrid approach for reducing false positives	Scalability issue
Kumari, A., & Mehta, A. K. (2020). A Hybrid Intrusion Detection System Based on Decision Tree and Support Vector Machine. <i>2020 IEEE 5th International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation (ICCCA)</i> , 396-400. https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCA49841.2020.9250753	How can combining Decision Tree and Support Vector Machine algorithms improve IDS performance?	Decision Tree, SVM with PSO	J48, SVM	KDD CUP	PSO with J48 and SVM	Accuracy: 99.2%, FPR: 0.9%	Hybrid approach with PSO improves accuracy and reduces false positives	High accuracy and low false positive rate	Scalability and computational cost
Landress, A. D. (2016). A hybrid approach to reducing the false positive rate in unsupervised machine learning intrusion detection. <i>Conference Proceedings - IEEE SOUTHEASTCON, 2016-</i> , 1-6. https://doi.org/10.1109/SECON.2016.7506773	How can a hybrid approach combining clustering, feature selection, and neural network techniques reduce the false positive rate?	Clustering, Feature Selection, Self-Organizing Maps	K-Means, J48 Decision Tree, SOM	KDD Cup 99	Clustering, Feature Selection, SOM	Accuracy: 99.96% FPR: 0.30397%	Clustering combined with SOM improves FPR and visualization	Improved visualization and false positive reduction	Computationally expensive
Ohta, S., Kurobayashi, R., & Kobayashi, K. (2005). Minimizing False Positives of a Decision Tree Classifier for Intrusion Detection on the Internet. <i>Journal of Network and Systems Management</i> , 10(4), 399-419. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10922-006-9162-4	How can a modified attribute evaluation function effectively reduce the false positive rate in IDS?	Proposed a new attribute evaluation function that replaces the traditional information-gain criterion.	C4.5 Decision Tree	KDD99	Attribute evaluation function replacing the information-gain criterion to suppress false positives.	FPR reduced to 22.2%–42.1% of original. Accuracy improved after leaf rewriting	The proposed attribute evaluation function significantly reduces false positives in Decision Tree classifiers.	- Practical applicability - Comprehensive evaluation using multiple datasets.	- Complexity in parameter tuning. - Potential for increased false negatives.
Pitre, P., Gandhi, A., Konde, V., Adhao, R., & Pachghare, V. (2022). An Intrusion Detection System for Zero-Day Attacks to Reduce False Positive Rates. <i>2022 International Conference for Advancement in Technology (ICONAT)</i> , 1-6. https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOAT53423.2022.9726105	How can feature selection and machine learning models be combined to improve detection of zero-day attacks?	Hybrid IDS model combining SVM, Decision Trees, and Logistic Regression	SVM, Decision Trees, Logistic Regression	CSE-CIC-IDS2018	Feature selection methods (Pearson, chi-squared, ANOVA) and fine-tuning	Accuracy: 95.1%, FPR: Improved in Stage 2	Two-stage hybrid IDS significantly reduces false positives and maintains detection accuracy	Strong reduction in false positives	Complex implementation and dataset dependency
Vasseur, P. R. (2018). <i>A machine learning approach to verify and reduce false positive alarms generated by data breach detection processes</i> (Order No. 13807340). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (2305833827). Retrieved from https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/machine-learning-approach-verify-reduce-false-alarms/docview/2305833827/sq-2	How can a machine learning approach using the ID3 algorithm reduce false positive alarms in data breach detection?	Iterative machine learning approach using ID3 Decision Tree	ID3 (Iterative Dichotomiser 3)	Data-in-motion and data-at-rest	Iterative learning feedback mechanism and automated feedback process	Accuracy: 100% in third validation phase, FPR: Decreased	Iterative retraining with expert feedback significantly reduces false positives	Adaptive learning and automated feedback	Relies on expert feedback and limited real-time applicability
Wu, S.-Y., & Yen, E. (2009). Data mining-based intrusion detectors. <i>Expert Systems with Applications</i> , 36(3), 5605-5612. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2008.09.138	How can classification trees and SVM improve intrusion detection and reduce false alarms?	SVM applied for classification; C4.5 for refining classifications	C4.5 (Decision Tree), SVM	KDD Cup 99	Optimization via Lagrange multipliers for SVM	- FPR: SVM better (lower FPR) - Detection: C4.5 better (Probe, U2R, DOS)	C4.5 outperforms SVM in reducing false alarms and improving detection rate	SVM struggles with datasets having a low proportion of normal data	Dataset is outdated for modern environments